

ADVANCING MANAGERIAL EXPERTISE THROUGH EDUCATION: COMPARATIVE UKRAINIAN AND GLOBAL PRACTICES

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Abstract: The article examines the peculiarities of professional training of managerial personnel in the field of education, using Ukrainian and foreign experience from 2020 to 2024. It considers the critical stages of the development of the Ukrainian pedagogical school and its transformation by modern challenges in the context of military conflict. International management training models, including legal, cultural, and ethical aspects that influence educational policy in the EU, the USA, and Asia, are described. The process of integrating the Ukrainian education system into the European educational space by implementing the Bologna Process and international exchange programmes is highlighted. Particular attention is paid to the impact of the war on the transformation of management training programmes in Ukraine. The problems of adapting curricula to crisis conditions and introducing psychological training with security measures are revealed. The critical components of the strategy for training managers in the context of hostilities on the territory of Ukraine are outlined, with a particular focus on the management of educational institutions in conditions of instability. The prospects for developing personnel training based on foreign experience in the post-war period are analysed. The application of international practices to restore educational infrastructure and improve professional competence is proposed. The article examines the role of digitalisation and innovative technologies in training modern managers who can act effectively in the face of change and crises. The importance of international cooperation in the educational sphere for improving the quality of management programmes in Ukraine is shown.

Keywords: Professional training, Management personnel, Educational institutions, Ukrainian educational school, Foreign experience, Crisis management, Globalisation of education

1 Introduction

The training of educational managers is an integral part of the development of the educational system of any country, as effective management of educational institutions determines the quality of the educational process. Modern training of managers of educational institutions involves developing managerial skills and integrating the latest scientific achievements into their activities. Particular attention is paid to creating conditions for forming a scientific community among the heads of educational institutions. Opportunities for professional growth include participation in scientific conferences, publications and exchange of experience at the international level. Management skills are formed through the development of critical thinking, research skills and an innovative approach to the organization of one's own work space. Human competencies are formed as a result of the expansion of educational services. High competition on the world market and the presence of qualified graduates play a significant role.

A comparison of European, American, and Ukrainian educational management programs reveals significant differences in approaches to the organization of education, management of educational processes, and development of managerial competencies. European programs often emphasize the most important: decentralized management, autonomy of educational institutions and innovative approaches to leadership. They have found their place in the Bologna process and EQF standards. American training programs for education managers are aimed at the development of individual leadership skills and the integration of management technologies into educational organizations, the so-called "American model of success". The Ukrainian system of training managers remained centralized until recent years. European standards are actively implemented

in the training of educational leaders thanks to the European integration course. Imitation of the best European and American models is necessary for further globalization of Ukrainian education (UN, 2015; Alcántara et al., 2023; Wodon, 2023). Nevertheless, the integration of the Ukrainian system into the global educational space will improve the quality of training and ensure compliance with global requirements for the management of educational institutions. In today's world, where technologies are developing at an incredible speed, digital tools are becoming an integral part of the training of managers in the field of education. The advantage is manifested as follows in the use of modern tools: digital platforms, software products for the administration of educational processes, separate servers. Distance learning systems are a measure of the effectiveness of educational institutions. In addition, these technologies facilitate the performance of administrative tasks, optimizing management processes.

In the conditions of the war in Ukraine, when due to hostilities, many educational institutions were forced to switch to remote mode of operation, the role of digital solutions in the educational sphere became even more significant. The forced transition accelerated the digitization process, where the following platforms were needed to support the continuity of the educational process: Moodle, Zoom, and Microsoft Teams. The use of digital tools allows managers to maintain the functioning of institutions in difficult wartime. There are also a number of advantages. The main one is the ability to quickly respond to new challenges, ensuring stable work even under conditions of political and economic instability. The integration of "mobile" technologies in the training of managers opens up prospects for the creation of new management models that improve the efficiency of educational institutions and contribute to their development.

Digital tools are becoming an integral part of the training of education managers. The use of software solutions for the management of educational processes simplifies administrative procedures, and this is a strategic goal of many higher educational institutions. Technology plays a key role in the full-scale war in Ukraine. Educational institutions are forced to switch to distance learning due to hostilities. The war accelerated the process of digitization of education. The use of Moodle, Zoom and Microsoft Teams platforms has become critical for ensuring the continuity of the educational process. Digital technologies are the key to balanced management, allowing managers to quickly adapt to changes and support the functioning of educational institutions in conditions of complete socio-economic uncertainty. The integration of digital tools into the management training system opens up new opportunities for developing modern management models and ensuring the effective operation of educational institutions.

2 Literature review

In recent years, the problem of training managers in education remains one of the most relevant topics for researchers. The success of the educational process and the general level of education in the country directly depends on how well organized "modern management" is in educational institutions. As Blasutto (2024) points out, the training of educational managers is a key element for the formation of a sustainable and competitive education system. In turn, Choi et al. (2023) focus on the fact that in the conditions of globalization and rapid digitization of educational processes, heads of educational institutions must be ready for new challenges of digital transformation and be able to effectively manage changes.

Kušec and Čikeš (2023) made a significant contribution to the comparison of European and American approaches to educational leadership. In their opinion, European programs for training educational leaders focus more on issues of

decentralization and autonomy of institutions, while in the American system more attention is paid to the individual development of leadership qualities and the ability to adapt to complex political and economic conditions. Xiang and Zeng (2023) emphasize that in the conditions of globalization, combining the best practices of European and American management training programs is a decisive factor. It is aimed at improving the quality of education systems in countries seeking reforms. The digital platforms Moodle and Zoom have become vital for the functioning of educational institutions (Langdon et al., 2023).

Research is increasingly focusing on digital tools for executive training. The work of Havryliuk and Boryn (2023) analyzes how the war affects the educational system in Ukraine. The main idea observed in the article is the strengthening of the development of digital platforms for distance learning as a key means of ensuring the continuity of the educational process even in the most difficult times. Langdon et al. (2023) add that digital tools have become an integral part of executive training. They must not only respond to challenges, but also quickly make decisions in crisis conditions.

The topic of training management personnel in education is currently the subject of many discussions among Ukrainian and foreign researchers. Tumienne et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of developing managerial competencies of educational leaders in order for them to cope with the challenges of today: digitalization and global crises. Accordingly, Pınarcıkoğlu (2023) investigates the issue of the quality of education – specialized training programs for educational managers that help improve the quality of management in educational institutions and positively affect educational outcomes.

An equally important aspect is the study of European educational programs for managers. According to a study by Hélot and Bonacina-Pugh (2023), training programs in the EU emphasize the decentralization of management and the use of innovative technologies. They note that the development of “leadership skills” and the ability to quickly adapt to changes is a priority for European heads of educational institutions. Similarly to Hélot, Gula L. (2023) and Gula O. (2023) emphasizes that the integration of best practices from different countries contributes to the formation of a more effective global education system, which is hard to disagree with.

Digital tools – are priority tools to support wartime learning and improve learning management. As Benstead et al. (2023) point out, the strategy to support learning in wartime is important now. They indicate that the use of distance technologies allows maintaining the “continuity” of the educational process and opens up new opportunities for improving management efficiency. This is also confirmed in the work of Bryl and Sabadin (2023). Researchers claim that innovative technologies contribute to the development of change and crisis management skills in managers.

Research aims. The purpose of this article is to investigate how the education management system in Ukraine is being transformed in the context of modern challenges caused by the full-scale war of 2022. Special attention is paid to the following question: how do digital technologies and international experience affect the improvement of the effectiveness of the training of educational managers? The article also analyzes how the adaptation of educational processes to new realities contributes to the development of the competencies of educational leaders. The study covers the differences between European, American and Ukrainian approaches to the training of educational leaders with a focus on the prospects for the globalisation of educational systems. The article analyses the adaptation of Ukrainian educational programmes to crisis conditions, including distance learning and innovative management methods (NACS, 2024). To achieve this goal, the article uses comprehensive approaches that combine the analysis

of managerial, educational and technological factors that directly impact the training system.

3 Research methods

The research methodology was based on the assessment of domestic and foreign systems of training management personnel in the field of education. For this purpose, a quantitative analysis of higher education institutions in Ukraine and their educational programmes and institutional features was carried out. Particular attention is paid to training managers in managing educational institutions in crises and reforming the education system. The study analysed 332 higher education institutions, including state, municipal and private universities, academies and institutes, which allowed us to identify the main trends and problems in the training of educational managers.

The main areas of the study were crisis management during the war, integration of digital technologies into educational processes, and development of leadership and communication skills among educational institution heads. The comparative analysis method was used to study the differences between Ukrainian and foreign practices of managerial training.

The sample consisted of executive education programmes in Ukraine, the United States, and the European Union, as these regions have a significant influence on global education policy and are closely involved in Ukraine's educational reforms. Critical management training programmes in Germany, the UK and France were studied to understand European standards in education. American approaches to the training of managers through the MBA programme with an educational focus were analysed, allowing comparison of different management practice models. This approach made it possible to draw conclusions about the compliance of Ukrainian approaches with international standards and identify possible areas for improvement.

The research methodology involved the use of qualitative methods of analysis. The study included an in-depth analysis of Ukrainian legislation and international regulatory documents regulating the education sector. The laws of Ukraine “On higher education” and “On education” were revised – they formulate the main requirements for the training of heads of educational institutions. Attention was also paid to the European Qualifications Framework – EQF and the standards of the Bologna process. Both are key in harmonizing Ukrainian educational programs with European ones. A comparative analysis of normative legal documents helped to reveal the fundamental principles of training heads of educational institutions in different countries (Hokkanen et al., 2019). The final stage of the research was the formation of conclusions. They concerned the main issue: to what extent the Ukrainian management training system meets international requirements and standards.

4 Results

Management training is critical in ensuring the effective management of organisations and educational institutions. It involves acquiring professional knowledge and developing competences for strategic decision-making, resource and team management. From a scientific point of view, professional training is based on a competence-based approach that focuses on developing managerial, communication and leadership skills. According to the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) classification, managers must have the knowledge and ability to apply it in complex and unpredictable situations. Lifelong learning is essential, as managers need to adapt to changing environments and constantly improve their knowledge. In the educational environment, this is manifested in the ability to manage the pedagogical process and resources and support innovative approaches to learning (Japir Bataineh et al., 2023).

In every country, education plays a crucial role in developing human capital, which is the basis for economic growth and social well-being. Educational institution managers shape the

country's future because the education system's effectiveness depends on its competences. According to Tkachenko (2021), in developed economies such as Finland, Japan or Germany, the quality of management of educational institutions is an essential component of success in the global market. According to CMU Resolution No. 286-p of 23 February 2022, in Ukraine, according to the Education 2030 strategy, management training is one of the priorities for reforming the education sector (KMU,

2022). An effective management system helps to create innovative educational models, introduce modern technologies and increase the competitiveness of graduates in the global labour market. The role of managers in this process is vital, as they ensure the integration of education into global processes. The characteristics of the programmes for training managers of educational institutions abroad are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of training programmes for heads of educational institutions in foreign countries

Country	Programme name	Universities	Programme duration
USA	Master of Education in Educational Leadership	Harvard University	Two years
USA	Principal Preparation Programme	University of Illinois	Two years
Germany (EU)	Schulleiterfortbildung	Humboldt University of Berlin	One year
United Kingdom (EU)	National Professional Qualification for Headship (NPQH)	University of Manchester	12-18 months

Source: developed by the authors

Educational leadership programmes in the United States and the European Union have a common goal: developing leadership skills and management competences and effectively managing educational institutions. In the United States, the Master of Education in Educational Leadership (Harvard University) and Principal Preparation Programme (University of Illinois) strongly emphasise innovation, technology integration, and the development of management strategies. In Germany and the United Kingdom, programmes are aimed at developing educational leadership, emphasising improving administrative management in education.

The development of such programmes in Ukraine has challenges in leadership training for higher education institutions, which require more specialised training due to the large number of universities and their strategic importance for the country's educational system. Currently, programmes are mainly focused on schools, which requires developing leadership training programmes specifically for higher education institutions. Only a few programmes at the higher education level at the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv and the National University of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy could train leaders to

manage large educational institutions. However, introducing management training programmes at universities requires investment and modernisation of education.

Higher education is one of the most challenging and responsible areas of management training. There are a large number of higher education institutions in the country that play a leading role in training personnel for various sectors of the economy. As of December 2022, there were 332 higher education institutions in Ukraine, of which 191 were state-owned, and 133 were subordinated to the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. Municipal HEIs account for 25 units, while the number of private institutions is 116. Five hundred fifty separate structural units are also involved in training. The total number of higher education students in Ukraine is 1,112,965, of which 869,365 are enrolled in institutions subordinated to the MES. This includes 727,848 bachelors, 316,623 masters and 32,859 postgraduate students (PhDs). These figures demonstrate the significant scale of the higher education system in Ukraine, which provides training for highly qualified specialists, including managers. The leading indicators of higher education institutions are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of higher education in Ukraine

Indicators	Meaning
Number of higher education institutions (universities, academies, institutes), units	332
– state	191
– of which are subordinated to the Ministry of Education and Science, units	133
– communal	25
– private	116
Separate structural subdivisions (institutes, academies, colleges) and colleges within the structure of higher education institutions, units	550
Destroyed higher education institutions, units	8
Total number of applicants (HEIs, HEEs), persons	1 112 965
of them in the institutions of the Ministry of Education and Science, units	869365
– junior specialist (educational qualification level)	31852
– junior bachelor	2880
– bachelor	727848
– specialist	778
– master	316623
– PhD	32859
– doctor of arts	125
Total number of researchers, research and teaching staff of legal entities, persons	161 385
of them in the institutions of the Ministry of Education and Science, persons	114045

Source: compiled based on (OsvitaUa, 2023)

Since gaining independence in 1991, Ukraine has been actively working to create its system of training management personnel in education. In the initial stages of reforming the educational system, an important task was to adapt Soviet management

models to the new conditions, including forming an independent pedagogical school and improving approaches to managerial training. One of the critical events in this process was the adoption of the Law of Ukraine "On Education" in 1996, which

laid the foundation for developing the higher education system and training pedagogical and managerial personnel. In the 2000s, there was a need to move to European standards in managing educational institutions, which was reflected in implementing the Bologna Process in Ukraine.

According to the strategies of the National Agency of Ukraine on Civil Service (2024), modern training education managers focus on introducing modular programmes, integrating information technology into management processes and using a competence-based approach. In 2017, a new Law on Education was adopted, which defined the key areas of reform in the sector to create conditions for the professional development of managers through a system of certification and continuing education. As of 2024, much attention is being paid to training leaders of educational institutions who can manage in times of war and implement a management style close to the digitalisation and globalisation of the educational process.

International management training has specific features determined by legal, cultural and ethical components. At the global level, management education programmes are guided by the standards of international organisations such as UNESCO – Resolution A/RES/70/1. and OECD – Resolution EDU/EDPC/RD(2019)7, which develop recommendations on the necessary competences for managing educational institutions (OECD, 2022). According to these organisations, in the EU, the USA and Canada, the legal requirements for managers of educational institutions include mandatory certification and a higher education degree, usually a master's degree in education management or public administration.

International management training programmes consider cultural and ethical aspects, which involve assessing national traditions and cultural values in managing educational institutions. According to Tkachenko (2021), much attention is paid to collectivism and subordination in Japan and South Korea. In the US and Western Europe, the emphasis is on the autonomy of

school and university leaders and individual responsibility. An essential part of international training is the development of intercultural competence, as managers often work in multinational teams or collaborate with educational organisations from different countries, which requires a deep understanding of cultural differences and the ability to establish communication between representatives of different cultures.

The integration of Ukraine's management training system into the global educational community is gradual and has several key stages. According to the CMU, one of the first steps was Ukraine's accession to the Bologna Process in 2005, which opened up opportunities for harmonising Ukrainian educational programmes with European standards. The integration involved adapting management training programmes to the requirements of the European Qualifications Framework. It includes modular learning, ECTS credits and the introduction of European-style diplomas.

In the 2010s, Ukrainian universities and institutes began to participate in the international exchange programme Erasmus+ actively. This allowed future managers to gain experience studying and training at foreign educational institutions. The integration also affected the legal framework: new legislative acts, such as the Law on Higher Education of 2014 and its update in 2020, have contributed to implementing international quality standards for training management professionals. Since 2022, the Law of Ukraine No. 2157-IX dated 24.03.2022 on reforming the educational system and adapting it to new challenges in the wartime environment has been in force. Cooperation with the European Union and other international organisations has provided access to best practices in managing educational institutions and created opportunities for further integration of Ukrainian personnel into the global education system. A comparison of the experience of training managers in Ukrainian and foreign educational institutions is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of Ukrainian and foreign experience in training of educational institution managers

Criterion	Ukrainian experience	Foreign experience
Training at the institutional level	Educational programmes at universities (Master's degree in educational management)	MBA programmes with a focus on educational leadership (USA, UK)
Certification of managers	Optional certification for management positions	Certification is mandatory in most EU and US countries
Professional development courses	Mandatory courses every five years	Annual courses with a focus on the latest trends in management
Training based on educational institutions	Mostly, theoretical studies at universities	Internships in schools and educational organisations as a mandatory part of the programme
Use of modern technologies	Limited use of information technology	Active use of EdTech, management platforms
Practical training	No or minimal internship	Strong emphasis on practical learning and leadership in education
Participation in international programmes	A limited number of exchange programmes	Extensive participation in exchange programmes and international cooperation
Management models	Traditionally centralised management model	Decentralised models with autonomy of schools and universities
Financing of training programmes	Funded by the state	Both public and private funding is available, as well as scholarships
Cooperation with international organisations	Partially integrated into international projects	Close cooperation with UNESCO, OECD and other international organisations

Source: developed by the authors based on (Batsenko, 2023; Bryl & Sabadin, 2023; Blasutto, 2024; Čikeš & Kušec, 2023; Choi et al., 2023; Corbett, 2023)

The full-scale war that has been going on in Ukraine since 2022 has caused irreparable damage to the education sector and affected the functioning of management training institutions. A significant number of educational institutions have been destroyed or damaged. According to the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, the hostilities affected eight higher education institutions. More than 1 million higher education students faced the need to adapt to new learning environments, including distance and blended learning. These circumstances require significant changes in approaches to the management of educational processes. Management training programmes have transformed: modules on crisis management, emergency

adaptation strategies, and digital skills development have been introduced to ensure the continuity of the learning process. The war is destroying educational institutions' material base and changing management approaches, forcing educators to respond to the challenges of the times and develop new competences for managers capable of acting effectively in a crisis.

In the context of the active phase of the war in Ukraine, the strategy for training management personnel should consider the conditions in which educational institutions operate. First, it is necessary to adapt educational programmes to new challenges. This includes introducing special courses in crisis management

that teach managers how to act in conditions of limited resources and instability. Psychological training of managers is an underestimated factor, as they should be prepared to provide support to teaching staff and students who have suffered psychological trauma as a result of military operations. Training in psychological assistance and burnout prevention has become a mandatory part of the training of modern managers. The security of educational institutions has become a priority for heads of

educational institutions. In the face of a military threat, managers must be prepared to evacuate quickly, create a safe, educational environment and cooperate effectively with security agencies. The three areas define the critical aspects of training personnel with the knowledge and skills to manage educational institutions in wartime. The specifics of managerial training with the relevant components in the three areas are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Peculiarities of managerial training in the context of a full-scale war

Source: developed by the authors

The post-war period opens up new prospects for developing the management training system in Ukraine, as the restoration of educational institutions will require qualified and well-trained managers. Using the foreign experience of Israel and Western Europe after the Second World War will be essential in restoring the management system. Foreign programmes that include elements of crisis management, digitalisation and adaptive management can be integrated into the Ukrainian education system. Ukraine's experience managing educational institutions during the war can be valuable for other countries because of its uniqueness. Further integration with the European education system will facilitate the introduction of the latest methods that will improve the quality of management training. In the post-war period, special attention will be paid to infrastructure development and raising the level of professional competence of managers, which will help restore educational institutions faster and ensure their stable operation.

5 Discussion

The results obtained on the training of management personnel in the field of education confirm the importance of integrating digital technologies into curricula. The study by Deale (2023) indicates the specifics of using digital technologies to improve modern professionals' management quality. Our findings align with Aydın (2023), who argues that leadership competences are a critical factor in the successful management of educational institutions. Similarly to Tumiene et al. (2022), our study has shown how European programmes focus on decentralising management and promoting educational institutions' autonomy. A common point of view is shared by Ortega-Rodríguez (2023), who demonstrates that American educational programmes focus on individual leadership skills.

In contrast, Ukrainian models remain more centralised. The findings correlate with the study by Johnny Artha et al. (2023),

which emphasises the need to integrate digital technologies into training managers in distance learning. Babenko's (2023) findings on reforming the Ukrainian education system confirm our findings on the importance of adapting educational programmes to the impact of war and digitalisation (Babenko, 2023). Our findings echo the research of Corbett (2023), who emphasizes the need for harmonization of training standards for educational managers in the context of globalization. Important parallels can also be drawn with the work of Vodon (2023), who emphasizes the importance of including anti-crisis management in educational programs to ensure the stability of educational institutions in the face of global changes. Machado Coden and Da Paixão (2023) notes in his research that digital learning platforms are becoming a key tool for training managers to work in crisis conditions. Similar to Iyengar et al. (2023), we believe that international cooperation in the field of education significantly contributes to the improvement of the level of training of educational leaders and helps to develop their professional competencies. Despite the common views of researchers, further study of issues of digitalization and management strategies in crisis situations remains a promising direction for future research.

6 Conclusion

The training of managerial personnel in the field of education is an extremely important factor for ensuring the effective functioning of educational institutions in the conditions of modern challenges. Despite the difficult political and economic conditions, the education system in Ukraine is gradually being reformed, approaching international standards. The study shows that the implementation of digital technologies in the process of training educational managers is a key means of maintaining the continuity of the educational process and ensuring effective management of institutions in crisis conditions. An important step is the introduction of new educational programs aimed at

management in crisis conditions. Such a complex of approaches becomes critically necessary for the successful development of educational institutions. In addition, it is important to strengthen the autonomy of educational institutions and develop leadership skills among their managers.

The obtained results confirm the chosen educational course of Ukraine – active cooperation with European and American educational institutions, which contributes to the globalization of the management training system. Thanks to the harmonization of educational standards and the exchange of experience with international partners, it was possible to significantly improve training programs and raise the level of training of educational managers. Special attention should be paid to further development of digital infrastructure. It is she who plays an important role in the management of educational processes in the conditions of modern challenges: war and post-war reconstruction. Using international experience will allow Ukraine to ensure the training of competent managers capable of effectively managing educational processes and promoting the sustainable development of the educational system at the national and international levels.

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